

<https://doi.org/10.70590/ice.2026.02.25>

<http://zoobank.org/urn:lsid:zoobank.org:pub:019DE81D-3A08-4960-916E-8F2420F91443>

● Review of the genus *Tridrepana* Swinhoe, 1895 (Lepidoptera, Drepanidae: Drepaninae) from Xizang, China

Xin-Hui YANG^{1,3}, Xia YU^{1,4} & Zhao-Hui PAN^{2,5*}

¹College of Plant Science, Xizang Agricultural and Animal Husbandry University, Linzhi 860000, Xizang, China

²Institute of Plateau Ecology, Xizang Agricultural and Animal Husbandry University, Linzhi 860000, Xizang, China

³<https://orcid.org/0009-0001-4007-7147>; 2298005275@qq.com

⁴<https://orcid.org/0009-0004-9703-5249>; 1120730931@qq.com

⁵<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4767-7962>; panzhaohui2005@163.com

*Corresponding author

Abstract: This paper reports five species of *Tridrepana* Swinhoe, 1895 (Lepidoptera, Drepanidae: Drepaninae) collected from Linzhi and Shigatse, Xizang, China, including three new Xizang records: *Tridrepana rubromarginata rubromarginata* (Leech, 1898), *Tridrepana marginata* (Watson 1957) and *Tridrepana crocea* (Leech, 1888). The adult morphology and genital characteristics of *Tridrepana rubromarginata indica* (Watson, 1957), *Tridrepana sadana* (Moore, 1865) and three new records in Xizang were described in detail, and the corresponding pictures and distribution from China and abroad were provided. It provides reference data for the study of Drepanidae in Xizang. All examined specimens are deposited in the Institute of Plateau Ecology, Xizang Agriculture and Animal Husbandry University.

Keywords: Drepaninae, genitalia, newly recorded species, *Tridrepana*, taxonomy

● 西藏黄钩蛾属（鳞翅目：钩蛾科：钩蛾亚科）记述

杨新慧¹，于霞¹ & 潘朝晖^{2*}

¹西藏农牧大学，植物科学学院，林芝 860000，西藏，中国

²西藏农牧大学，高原生态研究所，林芝 860000，西藏，中国

*通讯作者

摘要：本文报道了采集于中国西藏林芝市和日喀则市的黄钩蛾属（鳞翅目：钩蛾科：钩蛾亚科）5个物种，其中包含3个西藏新记录：*Tridrepana rubromarginata rubromarginata* (Leech, 1898)、*Tridrepana marginata* (Watson 1957)和*Tridrepana crocea* (Leech, 1888)。对*Tridrepana rubromarginata indica* (Watson, 1957)和*Tridrepana sadana* (Moore, 1865)以及3个西藏新记录的成虫形态和外生殖器的特征进行了详细描述，并提供相应的图片和国内外分布。为西藏钩蛾科昆虫区系研究提供参考数据。所有检视标本均保存于西藏农牧大学高原生态研究所。

关键词：钩蛾亚科，外生殖器，新记录种，黄钩蛾属，分类

Citation: Yang X-H, Yu X & Pan Z-H 2026: Review of the genus *Tridrepana* Swinhoe, 1895 (Lepidoptera, Drepanidae: Drepaninae) from Xizang, China. *The Indochina Entomologist*, 2 (25): 253–265. [杨新慧, 于霞 & 潘朝晖 2026: 西藏黄钩蛾属（鳞翅目：钩蛾科：钩蛾亚科）记述. 中南半岛昆虫学家, 2 (25): 253–265.]
<https://doi.org/10.70590/ice.2026.02.25>

Accepted by Cheng-Bin WANG: 13.IV.2026; published online: 17.IV.2026

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● Introduction

Tridrepana was founded by Swinhoe in 1895. There were four species: *T. albonotata*, *T. sadana*, *T. xanthoptera* and *T. vira* (= *Nordstroemia vira*) when the genus was founded, and no type species were specified until Warren (1922) designated *T. albonotata* as the type species of the genus. The species was initially classified in *Drepana* Schrank, thus clarifying the taxonomic status of the genus. In 1917, Nagano founded the monotypic genus *Konjikia* with *Drepana crocea* Leech as the model species. After the revision of Watson (1957), *Konjikia* was merged into the synonym of *Tridrepana*.

In the early stage, many scholars misclassified the insects of *Tridrepana* as related genera such as *Drepana*, *Agnidra*, *Callidrepana* and *Konjikia*, and the taxonomic hierarchy was confused (Warren 1903, 1922; Kirby 1892; Swinhoe 1895). Watson (1957) completed the systematic revision of the known species of this genus and clarified this problem. A total of 34 species and 24 subspecies were recorded, including 11 new species and 11 new subspecies. According to the characteristics of the wing spot, wing vein and foot distance of the adult external morphology and the male external genitalia, *Tridrepana* was divided into 7 species groups, namely *fulvata*, *albonotata*, *crocea*, *olivacea*, *postica*, *sadana* and *flava* species groups, which provided important information for subsequent scholars. Subsequent scholars mainly studied it regionally, and Inoue (1962) recorded two species distributed in Japan. Watson (1968) systematically combed the Chinese fauna for the first time, recording seven species. In 1972, Wilkinson published two new species *T. australaina* and *T. clinala* from Nepal. Holloway (1976) reported three species and one subspecies of Borneo, and revised *Tridrepana* in 1998 to record seven species and nine subspecies, including the new species *T. brunneilinea*. Chen (1985) published a new species *T. bifurcata* from China. Chu & Wang (1988) described 16 species and two subspecies, including four new species and one new subspecies, including five species groups. Song *et al.* (2011) described 19 species of this genus from China, including three new species, and revised two synonyms. Expósito-Hermosa (2020) describes a new species from the Philippines. After the above changes in the classification of species and the discovery of new species, 45 species of the genus have been recorded in the world, 19 species are distributed in China and 5 species are distributed in Xizang.

In this paper, we describe five species collected from *Tridrepana* Swinhoe, 1895 in southwestern Xizang, China, which increased the number of known species in Xizang from five to eight, providing reference data for the study of the fauna of hookworms in Xizang. A key to species and a checklist of known species of *Tridrepana* in China are also given.

● Material and methods

In this study, light trapping method was used to set up insect trapping sites in villages and towns of Linzhi City and Shigatse City in Xizang Autonomous Region, and fixed-point net trapping and light trapping of Drepanidae insect specimens were carried out. The required instruments are: 450 W high-pressure mercury lamp, lamp-induced collection cloth, glass bottle, 25 % ammonia water solution, absorbent cotton.

The adult pictures were taken by Canon 5D IV camera, and the clear pictures were synthesized with Helicon + Remote photo software. Photographs of the genitalia were taken using Leica S9i stereomicroscope. Use Adobe Photoshop 2023 to process images of adults and genitals. All examined specimens are deposited in the Insect Collection of the Institute of Plateau Ecology, Xizang Agricultural and Animal Husbandry University.

This paper mainly refers to the classification system of Chu & Wang (1988) and Watson (1957) for classification and identification. The terminology of adult and genital morphology follows Chu & Wang (1991), Hua (2005), Song *et al.* (2011) and Watson (1957, 1968).

Checklist of the Genus *Tridrepana* from China

***T. argentistriga* (Warren, 1896)**

Distribution. China (Hainan); Myanmar; Malaysia; Singapore; Indonesia.

***T. arikana arikana* (Matsumura, 1921)**

Distribution. China (Taiwan).

***T. arikana falcipennis* (Warren, 1922)**

Distribution. China (Guangdong, Guangxi); Bhutan.

***T. arikana emina* (Chu & Wang, 1988)**

Distribution. China (Hainan).

***T. bifurcata* (Chen, 1985)**

Distribution. China (Hainan, Yunnan, Xizang).

***T. bicuspidata* (Song, Xue & Han, 2011)**

Distribution. China (Hainan).

***T. crocea* (Leech, 1889)**

Distribution. China (Zhejiang, Hubei, Jiangxi, Hunan, Fujian, Guangxi, Sichuan, Yunnan, Xizang); Japan; Korea.

***T. fulva* (Hampson, 1893)**

Distribution. China (Xizang); India (Sikkim); Nepal.

***T. finita* (Watson, 1957)**

Distribution. China (Sichuan, Yunnan, Xizang).

***T. flava flava* (Moore, 1879)**

Distribution. China (Jiangxi, Fujian, Taiwan, Guangdong, Hainan, Guangxi, Yunnan); India, N. E. Himalaya.

***T. fulvata brevis* (Watson, 1957)**

Distribution. China (Shanghai, Fujian, Guangdong, Hainan, Hong Kong, Yunnan); India (Assam, Khasis); Myanmar.

***T. hainana* (Chu & Wang, 1988)**

Distribution. China (Hainan).

***T. hypha* (Chu & Wang, 1988)**

Distribution. China (Yunnan).

***T. maculosa* (Watson, 1957)**

Distribution. China (Sichuan, Yunnan).

***T. marginata* (Watson, 1957)**

Distribution. China (Yunnan, Xizang).

***T. rubromarginata rubromarginata* (Leech, 1898)**

Distribution. China (Gansu, Fujian, Sichuan, Yunnan, Xizang); India; Vietnam; Thailand.

***T. rubromarginata indica* (Watson, 1957)**

Distribution. China (Xizang); India (Sikkim, Tonglu); Bhutan; Nepal.

***T. sadana* (Moore, 1865)**

Distribution. China (Hubei, Xizang); India; Nepal; Myanmar.

T. subadelpha* (Song, Xue & Han, 2011)*Distribution.** China (Yunnan).***T. subunispina* (Song, Xue & Han, 2011)****Distribution.** China (Yunnan).***T. thermopasta* (Hampson, 1914)****Distribution.** China (Southwest China, Sichuan).***T. unispina* (Watson, 1957)****Distribution.** China (Fujian, Taiwan, Guangdong, Chongqing, Sichuan, Yunnan); Japan.**Key to the species of genus *Tridrepana* from Xizang**

1. The black spots on the wing surface and mid-cell are large; wing width.....2
The black spots on the wing surface and mid-cell are small; narrow wing shape.....*T. rubromarginata indica*
2. The forewing apex angle to inner edge has brown area; the outer edge of the forewing has no grayish white lines; the hind wing spots are brown and the boundary is not clear3
The brown area of the forewing does not reach the inner edge; the outer edge of the forewing has gray-white fine lines; the hind wing spots are black and the boundary is clear *T. sadana*
3. Female forewing outer edge is not bulging, straight *T. rubromarginata rubromarginata*
Female forewing outer edge is bulging, arcuate.....4
4. Female forewing apex angle slightly protruding, costal edge bulging, wing rounded; there's no gray in the freckles*T. marginata*
Female forewing apex angle bent down, sharp; marks with gray white*T. crocea*

● Taxonomy***Tridrepana rubromarginata* (Leech, 1898)***Drepana rubromarginata* Leech, 1898, *Trans. ent. Soc. Lond.*, 1898: 365. Holotype♂, China: Sichuan, Pu-tsu-Fong. (BMNH)*Iridrepana rubromarginata* Warren, 1922, in Seitz, *Macrolepid. World*, 10: 465.*Tridrepana rubromarginata* Watson, 1957, *Bull. Br. Mus. nat. Hist. (Ent.)*, 4: 484.

Diagnosis. This species is similar to *T. finita* (Watson, 1957) in wing shape and color. The difference is that *T. rubromarginata* has a brown area *T. finita* from the apex angle of the forewing to the near inner edge. In the male genitalia, the uncus margin is flatter than *T. finita*, with no sharp edges. There are two subspecies under this species. In adults, the wing shape of *T. rubromarginata indica* is narrower than that of the nominate subspecies, and the apex angle is more prominent. There are also differences in wing pattern and the male genitalia (see diagnosis under that species).

Distribution. China; India; Bhutan; Nepal.

FIGURES 1–8. *Tridrepana* adults: 1–2 *T. rubromarginata rubromarginata*: 1 male 2 female. 3–4 *T. rubromarginata indica*: 3 male 4 female. 5–6 *T. sadana* 5 male 6 female. 7 *T. marginata*, female. 8 *T. crocea*, female. Scale bars = 1.0 cm.

Tridrepana rubromarginata rubromarginata (Leech, 1898) (Newly recorded for Xizang)

Tridrepana rubromarginata rubromarginata Watson, 1957, *Bull. Br. Mus. nat. Hist. (Ent.)*, 4: 484.

Material examined: 1♂, 80K, Mêdog County, Linzhi City, Xizang, 20-VI-2025, collected by Zhaohui Pan, Xinhui Yang, Shuang Yang, Biao Zhao; 1♂, Shelter, Mêdog County, Linzhi City, Xizang, 24-VI-2025, collected by Zhaohui Pan, Xinhui Yang, Shuang Yang, Biao Zhao (Fig. 26); 1♂, Eastern Slope of Sejila Mountain, Linzhi City, Xizang, 3710 m, 30-VI-2020, collected by Enyong Chen; 1♀, Localizer station, Linzhi City, Xizang, 13-IX-2020, collected by Enyong Chen.

Diagnosis. Adult (Figs 1–2). This species is similar to *T. finita*, but can be identified by the following characteristics: adult forewing apex angle to inner edge has a brown shadow; the stripe boundary in the middle of wing is irregular. **Male genitalia (Figs 9–10).** Uncus broad, divided into two pieces, with fine hairs; socius finger; gnathos in cone-shaped, distributed small thorns; valvae short and width; saccus finger. Aedeagus slender, with dense cornuti at the caudal. The difference between *T. finita* and this species in male genitalia: uncus has horns at the edge, and valvae is larger. Aedeagus is short. **Male tergite and sternite (Figs 11–12).** Eighth tergite is trapezoidal, straight on both sides; Eight sternite is narrow and small, with intermediate protrusions. **Female genitalia (Fig. 21).** Ovipositor short, two oval processes near the ostium bursae. Apophyses anteriores are longer than apophyses posteriores. Ductus bursae short; corpus bursae round, no signum. The difference between *T. finita* and the species in the female genitalia: The circle between ovipositor and ostium is more round, apophyses anteriores and apophyses posteriores are shorter.

Distribution. China (Gansu, Fujian, Sichuan, Yunnan, Xizang); India; Vietnam; Thailand.

Tridrepana rubromarginata indica (Watson, 1957)

Tridrepana rubromarginata indica Watson, 1957, *Bull. Br. Mus. nat. Hist. (Ent.)*, 4: 486. Holotype ♂, India: Sikkim: Tonglo. (BMNH).

Material examined. 1♂, 62K, Mêdog County, Linzhi City, Xizang, 20-VII-2022, collected by Zhaohui Pan; 1♂, 80K, Mêdog County, Linzhi City, Xizang, 20-VI-2025, collected by Zhaohui Pan, Xinhui Yang, Shuang Yang, Biao Zhao; 1♂, West Slope of Sejila Mountain, Linzhi City, Xizang, 3330 m, 18-VII-2020, collected by Enyong Chen; 1♀, North Slope of Sejila Mountain, Linzhi City, Xizang, 3330 m, 25-22-VIII-2014, collected by Zhaohui Pan (Fig. 27).

Diagnosis. Adult (Figs 3–4). This species is similar to the nominate subspecies and *T. finita*, but can be identified by the following characteristics: the wing shape of adult is narrow and long; apical angle sharpness of forewing; there are two rows of brown spots starting from the inner edge of the hind wing submarginal line, but the outer row of the nominate subspecies only reaches the middle of the wing. **Male genitalia (Figs 13–14).** Uncus broad, divided into two pieces, with fine hairs; socius finger; gnathos is spherical, reaching the middle of Uncus; valvae short and width; saccus conical. Aedeagus slender, with dense cornuti at the end. The difference between *T. finita* and this species in male genitalia can be referred to the difference between *T. finita* and nominate subspecies. **Male tergite and sternite (Figs 15–16).** Eighth tergite is approximately rectangular, with radian on both sides and concave bottom; eight sternite is narrow and small, more prominent in the middle than nominate subspecies. **Female genitalia (Fig. 22).** Ovipositor short, two oval processes near the ostium bursae. Apophyses anteriores are as short as apophyses posteriores. Ductus bursae short; corpus bursae circle, no signum. The difference between *T. finita* and the species in the female genitalia: The circle between ovipositor and ostium is more round, apophyses anteriores and apophyses posteriores are shorter, and corpus bursae is larger than the species.

Distribution. China (Xizang); India; Bhutan; Nepal.

FIGURES 9–20. *Tridrepana* male genitalia and the eighth abdominal section: 9–12 *T. rubromarginata rubromarginata*: 9 valvae 10 aedeagus 11 tergite 12 sternite. 13–16 *T. rubromarginata indica*: 13 valvae 14 aedeagus 15 tergite 16 sternite. 17–20 *T. sadana* 17 valvae 18 aedeagus 19 tergite 20 sternite. Scale bars = 1.0 mm.

FIGURES 21–25. *Tridrepana* female genitalia: **21** *T. rubromarginata rubromarginata* **22** *T. rubromarginata indica* **23** *T. sadana* **24** *T. marginata* **25** *T. crocea*. Scale bars = 1.0 mm.

***Tridrepana sadana* (Moore, 1865)**

Drepana sadana Moore, 1865, *Proc. zool. Soc. Lond.*, 1865: 817. Holotype ♂, India: Darjeeling. (Collection of A. E. Russel. Lost.)

Platypteryx sadana Kirby, 1892, *Syn. Cat. Lepid. Het.*: 733.

Tridrepana sadana Swinhoe, 1895, *Trans. ent. Soc. Lond.*, 1895: 4.

Iridrepana sadana Warren, 1922, in Seitz, *Macrolepid. World*, 10: 466, pl.49: c.

Tridrepana adelpha Swinhoe sensu Chu & Wang, 1988, *Acta Entom. Sinica*, 31 (2): 204. (part).

Material examined. 1♂, Beibeng Township, Mêdog County, Linzhi City, Xizang, 18-13-V-2023, collected by Zhaohui Pan, Xinrui Jiang (Fig. 29); 1♂, Yigong Township, Bomi County, Linzhi City, Xizang, 8-IX-2018, collected by Zhaohui Pan; 1♂, Beibeng Township, Mêdog County, Linzhi City, Xizang, 10-V-2017, collected by Zhaohui Pan; 2♂, Chongse Village, Jilong Town, Jilong County, Shigatse City, Xizang, 24-VIII-2024, collected by Zhaohui Pan, Hai Luo, Litai Xie, Yi Zeng; 1♀, Hanmi, Medog County, Linzhi City, Xizang, 17-IX-2021, collected by Zhaohui Pan.

Diagnosis. Diagnosis. Adult (Figs 5–6). This species is similar to *T. finita*, but can be identified by the following characteristics: the apex angle of adult forewing is sickle-shaped; there is a gray-white stripe near the outer edge; there is a gray short stripe on the black spot above the middle of the forewing; the hind wing spots are clearer. **Male genitalia (Figs 17–18).** Uncus protrudes upwards into a triangle; socius finger; gnathos flat; valvae short and width; saccus is short and round. Aedeagus is short and cornuti is not visible. The male genitalia are similar to the two subspecies of *T. finita* and *T. rubromarginata*, and the main difference is that the inner-cornuti is not seen in the uncus shape and vesica, which can clearly distinguish the species. **Male tergite and sternite (Figs 19–20).** Eighth tergite is obviously different from similar species, with two bulges at the top and long hairs; the eight sternite is narrow and small, with a middle uplift. **Female genitalia (Fig. 23).** It is similar to the two subspecies of *T. rubromarginata*, but apophyses anteriores is shorter and apophyses posteriores is small and sharp.

Distribution. China (Xizang, Hubei); India; Nepal; Myanmar.

FIGURE 26. The habitat of *Tridrepana* spp.: Shelter, Mêdog County, Linzhi City, Xizang, China, 24-VI-2025 (photo by Yang Xin-Hui).

***Tridrepana marginata* (Watson, 1957) (Newly recorded for Xizang)**

Tridrepana marginata Watson, 1957, *Bull. Br. Mus. nat. Hist. (Ent.)*, 4: 490, figs 140–144, pl.3: 11. Holotype ♂, China: Yun nan: Lijiang. (ZFMK).

Material examined. 1 ♀, Meinu Lake, Chentang Town, Dingjie County, Shigatse City, Xizang, 3-IX-2024, collected by Zhaohui Pan, Hai Luo, Litai Xie, Yi Zeng (Fig. 28).

Diagnosis. Adult (Fig. 7). The forewing shape of this species is similar to that of *T. thermopasta*, but can be identified by the following characteristics: the top of the forewing front edge of the adult is bent inward; the apex angle is not significant, and the outer edge below it is retracted; there is a brown-yellow shadow covering the wing surface from the apex to the inner edge; there is a gray-white spot surrounded by a brown line in the middle of the shadow; the rear wing stripes are evenly distributed. **Female genitalia (Fig. 24).** Ovipositor short, margin serrate, ostium broad. Apophyses anteriores and apophyses posteriores are short. Ductus bursae slender; corpus bursae round, no signum.

Distribution. China (Xizang, Yunnan).

FIGURE 27. The habitat of *Tridrepana* spp.: Sejila Mountain, Linzhi City, Xizang, China, 27-VI-2025 (photo by Pan Zhao-hui).

***Tridrepana crocea* (Leech, 1889) (Newly recorded for Xizang)**

Drepana crocea Leech, 1888, *Proc. zool. Soc. Lond.*, 1888: 649. Holotype ♀ (described as male, in error), Japan. (BMNH)

Albara crocea Kirby, 1892, *Syn. Cat. Lepid. Het.*: 734.

Konjikia crocea Nagano, 1917, *Bull. Nawa ent. Lab.*, 2: 39.

Tridrepana crocea Inoue, 1956, *Check. List. Jap.*, 4: 369.

Tridrepana leva Chu & Wang, 1988, *Acta Entom. Sinica*, 31 (2): 204, fig. 2, pl.1: 5. Holotype ♂, China: Zhejiang: Tianmushan. syn. nov.

Material examined. 1 ♀, 80K, Mêdog County, Linzhi City, Xizang, 20-VI-2025, collected by Zhaohui Pan, Xinhui Yang, Shuang Yang, Biao Zhao.

Diagnosis. Adult (Fig. 8). The forewing shape of this species is similar to that of *T. unispina* and *T. hainana*, but can be identified by the following characteristics: the apex angle of the adult is sickle-shaped, the outer edge below it is adducted, and brown hair scales are distributed; there is a color band composed of black spots between the R₄-M₃ veins on the outer edge; there are white-gray spots in the middle of the spots on the front and rear wings.

Female genitalia (Fig. 25). Ovipositor is short, and there are two oval protrusions near the ostium. Apophyses posteriores are slightly longer than apophyses anteriores. Ductus bursae slender, ossification; corpus bursae is oval, with a thin strip of signum. Vas deferens slender, spermatheca with ossified linear stripes.

Similar to *T. unispina* in the female genitalia, the difference is that the signum on the corpus bursae is larger and lower.

Distribution. China (Xizang, Hainan).

FIGURE 28. The habitat of *Tridrepana* spp.: Meinu Lake, Chentang Town, Dingjie County, Shigatse City, Xizang, China, 3-IX-2024 (photo by Pan Zhao-hui).

FIGURE 29. The habitat of *Tridrepana* spp.: Beibeng Township, Mêdog County, Linzhi City, Xizang, China, 18-13-V-2023 (photo by Pan Zhao-hui).

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● Additional information

Author contributions: Conceptualization: X-H Yang. Resources: Z-H Pan & X Yu. Supervision: Z-H Pan & X Yu. Visualization: X-H Yang, Z-H Pan & X Yu. Writing - Original Draft: X-H Yang. Writing - Review & Editing: Z-H Pan.

Conflict of interest: The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Data availability: All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

Ethical statement: No ethical statement was reported.

Funding: 2025 Linzhi City Science and Technology Plan Project ‘Study on Species Diversity of Notodontidae Insects in Linzhi Area’ (Grant No.: XDHZ-2025-10), the Xizang Autonomous Region Science and Technology Plan Project ‘Investigation on Notodontidae Insects in Xizang and Compilation of Illustrated Handbook of Notodontidae in Xizang’ (Grant No.: XZ202501ZY0053), the Postgraduate Innovation Program of Xizang Agriculture and Animal Husbandry University ‘Taxonomic study of Drepanidae in Linzhi (Nyingchi), Xizang’ (Grant No. YJS-2025-09), and the Doctoral Program in Forestry of Xizang Agricultural and Animal Husbandry University (Phase I) (Grant No.: 533325001).

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Photo Gallery

月目大蚕蛾 *Saturnia zuleika* Hope, 1843
Gulinjing [古林箐], Yunnan
photograph by Tian-Jiao WANG [王天骄]